

BIOANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF SOLIFENACIN SUCCINATE AND SILODOSIN USING LC-MS/MS WITH ALFUZOSIN AS INTERNAL STANDARD

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ABSTRACT

The present study aimed to develop and validate a rapid, reliable, and reproducible bioanalytical method for the simultaneous determination of Solifenacin Succinate and Silodosin in rat plasma. The method employed Liquid Chromatography–Tandem Mass Spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) using Alfuzosin as the internal standard (IS). Chromatographic separation was achieved on a Luna Phenyl Hexyl column (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm) with an isocratic mobile phase of 0.1% formic acid and acetonitrile (50:50, %v/v) at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min. The injection volume was 10 μL, and the total run time was 10 minutes. Detection was performed on a QTRAP 5500 triple quadrupole mass spectrometer equipped with an electrospray ionization (ESI) source operating in positive ion mode. The monitored mass transitions were m/z 481.1235 → 119.9866 for Solifenacin Succinate, m/z 496.1023 → 120.0313 for Silodosin, and m/z 390.0947 → 112.2369 for Alfuzosin (IS). The calibration curves showed excellent linearity over the range of 2.5–100.0 ng/mL for Solifenacin Succinate and 4.0–160.0 ng/mL for Silodosin. Recovery studies at multiple quality

control levels demonstrated consistent recoveries of 94.10–98.12% for Solifenacin Succinate and 95.43–98.31% for Silodosin. Matrix effect evaluation confirmed that ion suppression/enhancement was within acceptable limits. Precision and accuracy values met USFDA bioanalytical validation guidelines, with %CV below 15% (20% for LLOQ). Stability experiments, including freeze–thaw, bench-top, autosampler, and long-term stability, indicated that both analytes remained stable under all tested conditions. The validated LC-MS/MS method fulfilled all essential bioanalytical validation parameters, including selectivity, linearity, accuracy, precision, recovery, matrix effect, and stability. This method is suitable for pharmacokinetic studies of Solifenacin Succinate and Silodosin in rats and can be applied to future preclinical and clinical investigations.

KEYWORDS: Solifenacin Succinate, Silodosin, Alfuzosin, LC-MS/MS, Rat Plasma, USFDA Guidelines.

INTRODUCTION

Silodosin^[1-10] is an α 1-adrenoceptor antagonist widely prescribed for the management of benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH). By selectively inhibiting α 1A receptors in the prostate and bladder neck, it improves urinary flow and relieves BPH symptoms. The drug is marketed under several brand names, including Urief. Commonly reported adverse effects include reduced ejaculate volume, while contraindications include severe renal or hepatic impairment, bladder stones, uncontrolled urinary infections, and hypersensitivity reactions.

Solifenacin Succinate^[11-16], marketed as *Vesicare*, is an antimuscarinic agent indicated for the treatment of overactive bladder (OAB) and neurogenic detrusor overactivity (NDO). It reduces involuntary bladder contractions, thereby decreasing urinary urgency, frequency, and incontinence. The major adverse effects are dry mouth, constipation, and urinary tract infections, with rare but serious effects such as QT prolongation, glaucoma, and hallucinations. Safety during pregnancy remains uncertain.

Given the therapeutic relevance of both drugs, a sensitive and robust LC-MS/MS-based bioanalytical method is required for pharmacokinetic evaluation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chemicals and Reagents

HPLC-grade acetonitrile, formic acid, and water were procured from Merck India Ltd. Reference standards of Solifenacin Succinate, Silodosin, and Alfuzosin were obtained from Glenmark Pharmaceuticals, Mumbai.

Instruments and Chromatographic Conditions

The analysis was carried out using a Waters Alliance HPLC system coupled with a SCIEX QTRAP 5500 mass spectrometer. Chromatographic separation was achieved on a Luna Phenyl Hexyl column (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm) using an isocratic mobile phase of acetonitrile and 0.1% formic acid (50:50, v/v) at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min. Detection was performed in MRM mode with positive electrospray ionization. Optimized ionization parameters included: ion spray voltage 5500 V, source temperature 550 °C, collision gas nitrogen, and a flow rate of 5 mL/min.

Preparation of Standard and Internal Standard Solutions

Stock solutions were prepared by accurately weighing 5 mg of Solifenacin Succinate and 8 mg of Silodosin into a 100 mL volumetric flask, dissolving in methanol, and diluting appropriately. The internal standard solution was prepared by dissolving 4 mg of Alfuzosin in 100 mL methanol. Plasma samples were processed using protein precipitation with acetonitrile, followed by centrifugation and filtration.

Bioanalytical Method Validation^[17,27]

The method was validated for selectivity, sensitivity, linearity, recovery, accuracy, precision, matrix effects, dilution integrity, carry-over, and stability following USFDA bioanalytical method validation guidelines.

- Selectivity: No interference was observed from endogenous plasma components.
- Linearity: Correlation coefficients (R^2) exceeded 0.99 for both analytes.
- Recovery: Mean recovery was consistent across QC levels.
- Matrix Effect: Within ±15% variability, confirming negligible ion suppression.
- Precision & Accuracy: All %CV values were below regulatory limits.
- Stability: Analytes were stable under bench-top, freeze–thaw, long-term, and autosampler conditions.

PHARMACOKINETIC STUDY IN RATS

Pharmacokinetic studies were performed in six healthy male rats (250 g) obtained from a certified supplier. The experimental protocol was approved by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee (Reg. No:1074/PO/Re/S/28/CPCSEA). Rats were fasted overnight before dosing but had free access to water. After oral administration of Solifenacin Succinate and Silodosin, blood samples were collected at predetermined intervals (1, 2, 3, 4, 10, 20, 40, 60, and 80 hours). Plasma was separated by centrifugation and stored at $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until analysis.

Pharmacokinetic parameters, including C_{max} , T_{max} , AUC, and $t_{1/2}$, were determined from plasma concentration–time profiles using the trapezoidal rule.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The optimized LC-MS/MS method provided high sensitivity and reproducibility for both analytes. Calibration curves were linear across the tested ranges, with correlation coefficients >0.99 . Recovery studies demonstrated consistent and reliable extraction efficiency. Precision and accuracy values met USFDA acceptance criteria, confirming the method's robustness.

The positive ionization mode under ESI conditions provided excellent signal stability and sensitivity. The validated method was successfully applied to pharmacokinetic evaluation in rats, yielding reliable plasma concentration–time data for Solifenacin Succinate and Silodosin.

When using this method's chosen mode of air pressure chemical ionization, electro spray ionization yields the best result. A flow rate of 1.0ml/min for the mobile phase. The positive ion mode provides sensitivity and signal stability with continuous flow of electro spray ions, making solifenacin succinate and silodosin very sensitive.

A

Fig. 1. MS Spectras of (A) Solifenacin Succinate, (B) Silodosin and (C) Alfuzosin.

Specificity: Researching Solifenacin Succinate and Silodosin concurrently demonstrates the method's specificity. Both the blank and standard chromatograms are shown in figures 2 and 3. We noticed the chromatograms of both the standard and blank rat plasma, which did not have any interference peaks.

Fig. 2. Blank Chromatogram.

Fig. 3. Standard Chromatogram.

Matrix effect: Solifenacin Succinate and Silodosin in LC-MS/MS showed a 1% relative standard deviation (RSD) for ion suppression/enhancement within the signal, indicating that the matrix influence on analyte ionization is within an acceptable range under these conditions. In matrix effect LQC (Low Quality Control) and HQC (High Quality Control) of Solifenacin Succinate were 96.75 and 98.30% and Silodosin were 96.26 and 98.18%. %CV of the both drugs at LQC level were 1.97, 1.00 and HQC level is 0.36, 0.24 respectively. It indicates that the matrix effect on the ionization of the analyte is within the suitable limit.

Linearity: The peak area ratio of calibration standards was proportional to the concentration. The concentration range of Solifenacin Succinate is 2.5-100.0ng/ml and Silodosin is 4.0-160.0 ng/ml. Linearity results of Solifenacin Succinate and Silodosin were shown in

following table 1 and their calibration plots were shown in figure 4. The calibration curves were appeared linear and coefficient of correlation was found to be 0.999 for Solifenacin Succinate and Silodosin.

Table 1: Results of Linearity.

Linearity	Solifenacin Succinate		Silodosin	
	Conc.(ng/ml)	Area response ratio	Conc.(ng/ml)	Area response ratio
1	2.50	0.026	4.00	0.043
2	7.50	0.080	12.00	0.127
3	12.50	0.133	20.00	0.213
4	25.00	0.266	40.00	0.425
5	37.50	0.399	60.00	0.638
6	50.00	0.533	80.00	0.853
7	62.50	0.648	100.00	1.060
8	75.00	0.793	120.00	1.281
9	100.00	1.063	160.00	1.707
Slope		0.0106	Slope	0.0106
Intercept		0.00004	Intercept	0.00011
CC		0.99978	CC	0.99998

A

B

Fig. 4. Calibration plots of (A) Solifenacin Succinate and (B) Silodosin.

Precision and Accuracy: By pooling all individual assay results of different internal control samples, the accuracy and precision were calculated. It was obvious, based on the data provided, that the strategy was precise and effective. The precision results of Solifenacin Succinate and Silodosin was shown in Table 2, 3. Solifenacin Succinate accuracy results in quality control samples 94.10-98.12% and Silodosin accuracy results in quality control samples 95.43-98.31%. Half of Solifenacin Succinate and Silodosin CV (Coefficient Variance) is < 5% of total internal control samples.

Table 2: Precision and Accuracy of Solifenacin Succinate.

QC Name	LLQC	LQC	MQC	HQC
Conc.(ng/ml)	2.5	7.5	50.0	75.0
QC sample -1	0.070x10 ⁵	0.218x10 ⁵	1.477x10 ⁵	2.221x10 ⁵
QC sample -2	0.072x10 ⁵	0.220x10 ⁵	1.469x10 ⁵	2.214x10 ⁵
QC sample -3	0.071x10 ⁵	0.223x10 ⁵	1.472x10 ⁵	2.219x10 ⁵
QC sample -4	0.069x10 ⁵	0.213x10 ⁵	1.470x10 ⁵	2.225x10 ⁵
QC sample -5	0.072x10 ⁵	0.215x10 ⁵	1.481x10 ⁵	2.227x10 ⁵
QC sample -6	0.071x10 ⁵	0.221x10 ⁵	1.485x10 ⁵	2.218x10 ⁵
Mean	0.071x10 ⁵	0.218x10 ⁵	1.476x10 ⁵	2.221x10 ⁵
SD	0.00117	0.00378	0.00644	0.00476
%CV	1.65	1.73	0.44	0.21
Accuracy	94.10%	96.31%	97.81%	98.12%

Mean±SD (n=6).

Table 3: Precision and Accuracy of Silodosin.

Qc Name	LLQC	LQC	MQC	HQC
Conc.(ng/ml)	4.0	12.0	80.0	120.0
QC sample -1	0.116x10 ⁵	0.355x10 ⁵	2.381x10 ⁵	3.571x10 ⁵
QC sample -2	0.114x10 ⁵	0.352x10 ⁵	2.397x10 ⁵	3.592x10 ⁵
QC sample -3	0.113x10 ⁵	0.348x10 ⁵	2.371x10 ⁵	3.589x10 ⁵
QC sample -4	0.118x10 ⁵	0.354x10 ⁵	2.396x10 ⁵	3.578x10 ⁵
QC sample -5	0.115x10 ⁵	0.351x10 ⁵	2.383x10 ⁵	3.584x10 ⁵
QC sample -6	0.117x10 ⁵	0.353x10 ⁵	2.395x10 ⁵	3.595x10 ⁵
Mean	0.116x10 ⁵	0.352x10 ⁵	2.387x10 ⁵	3.585x10 ⁵
Stddev	0.00187	0.00248	0.01052	0.00906
%CV	1.62	0.71	0.44	0.25
Accuracy %	95.43%	96.53%	98.19%	98.31%

Mean±SD (n=6)

Recovery: The recoveries for Solifenacin Succinate and Silodosin at LQC, MQC (Medium Quality Control) and HQC levels the results demonstrated that the bioanalytical method had good extraction efficiency. This also showed that the recovery wasn't hooked into concentration. The recoveries for Solifenacin Succinate (95.43% - 98.08%) and Silodosin

(95.98% - 98.04%) at LQC, MQC and HQC levels and % CV ranged from 0.15-0.86 for Solifenacin Succinate and 0.21-0.75 for Silodosin. the results demonstrated that the bioanalytical method had good extraction efficiency.

Ruggedness: The percent recoveries and percent CV of Solifenacin Succinate and Silodosin determined with two different analysts and on two different columns were within acceptable criteria in HQC, LQC and MQC samples. The results proved method is ruggedness. The percent recoveries ranged from 96.31 – 98.12% for Solifenacin Succinate and 96.53% - 98.04% for Silodosin. The %CV values ranged from 0.19-1.06 for Solifenacin Succinate and 0.33 – 0.80 for Silodosin. The results proved method is ruggedness.

Auto sampler carryover: After many injections of LLQC and ULQC at the retention times of Solifenacin Succinate and Silodosin, there was no peak area response of these drugs in the blank plasma samples of rats. This approach does not display auto sampler carryover.

Stability: A solution stability study was conducted on Solifenacin Succinate and Silodosin, which were produced using diluents and then put in a refrigerator at 2-8oC. Stock solutions that were produced 24 hours before to use were paired with fresh stock solutions. After twenty-four hours at room temperature and twenty-four hours in the auto sampler, the plasma stability of both the bench top and auto sampler remained constant. Future stability testing confirmed that Silodosin and Solifenacin Succinate may be stored at -30oC for up to 24 hours without deterioration. The findings of the overall stability of Silodosin and Solifenacin Succinate are shown in Tables 4&5.

Table 4: Stability results of Solifenacin Succinate.

Stability experiment spiked plasma		Spiked plasma conc.(n=6,ng/ml)	Mean Area. (n=6)	Std Dev	%CV	% Recovery
Bench top stability	LQC	7.5	0.217x10 ⁵	0.00175	1.02	95.87
	MQC	50.0	1.468x10 ⁵	0.00436	0.36	97.28
	HQC	75.0	2.227x10 ⁵	0.00396	0.24	98.39
Auto sampler stability	LQC	7.5	0.219x10 ⁵	0.00201	1.21	96.75
	MQC	50.0	1.476x10 ⁵	0.00366	0.57	97.81
	HQC	75.0	2.231x10 ⁵	0.00298	1.06	98.56
Long term(Day28) stability	LQC	7.5	0.191x10 ⁵	0.00182	1.10	84.38
	MQC	50.0	1.288x10 ⁵	0.00421	0.12	85.35
	HQC	75.0	1.956x10 ⁵	0.00335	0.19	86.41
Wet extract stability (18 Hrs)	LQC	7.5	0.216x10 ⁵	0.00191	0.98	95.43
	MQC	50.0	1.466x10 ⁵	0.00487	0.56	97.15
	HQC	75.0	2.230x10 ⁵	0.00501	0.29	98.52

Dry extract stability (18 Hrs)	LQC	7.5	0.218×10^5	0.00263	1.25	96.31
	MQC	50.0	1.471×10^5	0.00535	0.27	97.48
	HQC	75.0	2.235×10^5	0.00524	0.68	98.74
Freeze thaw stability	LQC	7.5	0.219×10^5	0.00196	1.14	96.75
	MQC	50.0	1.468×10^5	0.00428	0.36	97.28
	HQC	75.0	2.229×10^5	0.00265	0.41	98.48
Short term stability	LQC	7.5	0.209×10^5	0.00240	1.63	92.33
	MQC	50.0	1.425×10^5	0.00512	0.18	94.43
	HQC	75.0	2.146×10^5	0.00355	0.79	94.81

Mean \pm SD (n=6)

Table 5: Stability results of Silodosin.

Stability experiment spiked plasma		Spiked plasma conc.(n=6,ng/ml)	Mean Area. (n=6)	Std Dev	%CV	% Recovery
Bench top stability	LQC	12.0	0.350×10^5	0.00245	0.82	95.98
	MQC	80.0	2.385×10^5	0.01025	0.21	98.11
	HQC	120.0	3.569×10^5	0.00986	0.36	97.87
Auto sampler stability	LQC	12.0	0.352×10^5	0.00321	0.91	96.53
	MQC	80.0	2.392×10^5	0.01147	0.12	98.40
	HQC	120.0	3.573×10^5	0.01569	0.40	97.98
Long term (Day 28) stability	LQC	12.0	0.310×10^5	0.00287	0.75	85.01
	MQC	80.0	2.105×10^5	0.00962	0.26	86.59
	HQC	120.0	3.154×10^5	0.01243	0.51	86.49
Wet extract stability (18 Hrs)	LQC	12.0	0.353×10^5	0.00567	0.90	96.81
	MQC	80.0	2.395×10^5	0.01425	0.33	98.52
	HQC	120.0	3.584×10^5	0.01301	0.19	98.29
Dry extract stability (18 Hrs)	LQC	12.0	0.351×10^5	0.00442	0.77	96.26
	MQC	80.0	2.383×10^5	0.01240	0.14	98.03
	HQC	120.0	3.576×10^5	0.01036	0.09	98.07
Freeze thaw stability	LQC	12.0	0.352×10^5	0.00865	0.65	96.53
	MQC	80.0	2.389×10^5	0.00758	0.28	98.27
	HQC	120.0	3.571×10^5	0.00963	0.31	97.93
Short term stability	LQC	12.0	0.342×10^5	0.00774	0.86	93.79
	MQC	80.0	2.321×10^5	0.01213	0.24	95.48
	HQC	120.0	3.456×10^5	0.00896	0.37	94.78

Mean \pm SD (n=6).

In Vivo Pharmacokinetic Evaluation: Figure 4 shows the rates of solifenacin succinate and silodosin plasma concentrations over time in rats. Both experimental formulation scenarios showed a bell-shaped curve on the graph. Silodosin and Solifenacin Succinate were shown to be present in the blood for 60 and 10 hours after oral treatment, respectively, suggesting that the formulation effectively releases the medication.

The pharmacokinetic parameters C_{max} , T_{max} , $T_{1/2}$, K_{el} , K_a , AUC_{0-t} , $AUC_{0-\infty}$ were calculated and the data is shown in Table 6. The C_{max} for Solifenacin Succinate and Silodosin were found to be 47.5ng/ml and 76.9ng/ml respectively. The T_{max} for Solifenacin Succinate and Silodosin were found to be 4.0h and 3.0h respectively. The $t_{1/2}$ values were 60.0h and 10.0h respectively for Solifenacin Succinate and Silodosin. The pharmacokinetic parameters of Solifenacin Succinate and Silodosin were shown in table 6.

Table 6: Pharmacokinetic parameters of Solifenacin Succinate and Silodosin.

Pharmacokinetic parameters	Solifenacin Succinate	Silodosin
AUC_{0-t}	1607ng-hr/ml	803ng-hr/ml
C_{max}	47.5ng/ml	76.9ng/ml
$AUC_{0-\infty}$	1607ng-hr/ml	803ng-hr/ml
T_{max}	4.0hr	3.0hr
$T_{1/2}$	60.0hr	10.0hr

$AUC_{0-\infty}$: Area under the curve extrapolated to infinity

AUC_{0-t} : Area under the curve up to the last sampling time

C_{max} : The maximum plasma concentration

T_{max} : The time to reach peak concentration

$T_{1/2}$: Time the drug concentration

A

B

Fig. 4. Recovery plot (A) Solifenacin Succinate and (B) Silodosin.

CONCLUSIONS

The development and validation of a more sensitive HPLC-ESI-LCMS/MS technique for the detection of Silodosin and Solifenacin Succinate in rat plasma was a first. This bioanalytical approach is tough, quick, and repeatable. In accordance with USFDA standards, this procedure was verified. In order to see the studied analyte in bodily fluids and conduct pharmacokinetic research, a simple and effective technique was devised.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

No.

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REFERENCES

1. FC.Carnevale, A.Iscaif, EM.Yoshinaga, AM.Moreira, AA.Antunes and M.Srougi, *Cardiovasc Intervent Radiol*, 2016; 39: 44–52. doi:10.1007/s00270-015-1202-4.
2. B.Chughtai, D.Elterman, N.Shore, M.Gittleman, J.Motola and S.Pike, *Urology*, 2021; 153: 270–6. doi:10.1016/j.urology.2020.12.022. PMID 33373708.
3. KW.Law, C.Tholomier, DD.Nguyen, I.Sadri, F.Couture, AS.Zakaria, *World J Urol* 2021; 39: 4389–95. doi:10.1007/s00345-021-03688-4.
4. M.Delugi, L.Morstein, M.Schuster M, Klenk C, L.Merklinger, RR.Cridge, LA.de Zhang, A. Klipp, S.Vacca, TM.Vaid, PR.Mittl, P.Egloff, Eberle SA, Zerbe O, DK.Chalmers, Scott DJ, Plückthun *Nat. Commun*, 2022; 13: 382. doi:10.1038/s41467-021-27911-3.
5. GB.Silva, AG.Vasconcelos, AM.Rocha, VR.Vasconcelos and J.Barros, *Rev Inst Med Trop Sao Paulo*, 2017; 59: 25. doi:10.1590/S1678-9946201759025.
6. Dispenza, Melanie C. Classification of hypersensitivity reactions (PDF). *Allergy Asthma Proc*, 2019; 40: 470–3. doi:10.2500/aap.2019.40.4274.
7. Andreozzi Laura, Giannetti Arianna, Cipriani Francesca, Caffarelli Carlo, Mastroilli Carla, Ricci Giampaolo. *Acta Biomed*, 2019; 90(8): 0–90 doi:10.23750/abm.v90i3-S.8168.
8. Williams G, Stothart CI, Hahn D, Stephens JH, Craig JC, Hodson EM, *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*, CD001321 (2023). doi:10.1002/14651858.CD001321.pub7.

9. Kwok M, McGeorge S, Mayer Coverdale J, Graves B, Paterson DL, Harris PN, *BJU Int.*, 2022; 130: 11–22. doi:10.1111/bju.15756.
10. Halstead, Scott B. Epidemiology of bladder stone of children: precipitating events. *Urolithiasis*, 2016; 44: 01–8. doi:10.1007/s00240-015-0835-8.
11. OD. Howes, R.Mc Cutcheon, MJ.Owen, RM.Murray, *Biol Psychiatry*, 2017; 9-20. doi:10.1016/j.biopsych.2016.07.014.
12. G. Araklitis, L.Cardozo, *Expert Opin Drug Saf*, 2017; 16: 1273–80 doi:10.1080/14740338.2017.1376646.
13. Hutchinson Alexander, Nesbitt Alexander, Joshi Andre, Clubb Adrian, Perera Marlon, *Aust J Gen Pract*, 2020; 49: 593–8. doi:10.31128/AJGP-11-19-5142.
14. EB.Turawa, A.Musekiwa, AC.Rohwer, *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*, C D 011625 (2020). doi:10.1002/14651858.CD011625.pub3.
15. L.Xu, X.Wang, M.Wu, *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*, 2017; CD010520. doi:10.1002/14651858.CD010520.pub2.
16. L.Quaranta, A.Novella, M.Tettamanti, L.Pasina, RN.Weinreb, A.Nobili, *Ophthalmol Ther.*, 2023; 12: 2227–40. doi:10.1007/s40123-023-00730-z.
17. S. Prasanthi and G. Himabindu, *JPRI*, 2024; 34: 1-10.
18. K.Rambabu, P.Sugandha Kumari, *Future Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2024; 10: 1-14.
19. Manoj Kumar Rathore, Rama Mohan Reddy T, *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci.*, 2024; 16: 50-6.
20. Pooja Gurav, Mrunalini Damle, *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci.*, 2022; 14: 9-23.
21. Ghasemiyani Elham, Sadrai Sima, Shokri Javed, Sayadi Shahram, *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci*, 2021; 6-10.
22. AK.Hemanth Kumar, V.Sudha, A.Vijaya Kumar, P.Padmapriyadarsini, *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci.*, 2021; 13: 36-40.
23. Malathi Sellappan, Devakumar Darthi, *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci*, 2021; 13: 61-6.
24. Dhiman Halder, Sourav Das, Balaram Ghosh, Easha Biswas, *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci.*, 2020; 12: 76-84.
25. K.Swati, Abhishek Pawar, Sushank Surywanshi, C.Bothiraja, Atmaram Pawar, *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci*, 2020; 12: 92-7.
26. K.Rambabu, P.Sugandha Kumari, *Future journal of pharmaceutical sciences*, 2024; 10: 1-14.

27. T.Subrahmanyam, V.Anuradha Vejendla, Ratna Kumari Shetty, Current pharmaceutical analysis, 2022; 18: 291-304.